

PRACTICAL ISSUES OF DEVELOPING METHODOLOGICAL
COMPETENCE IN FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

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Abstract. The article describes the practical results of developing methodical competence in future music teachers. Also, the article contains some comments on the competence of the future music teacher, the ability to organize the educational process.

Keywords. Development, education, research, educational process, development, environment, methodological competence, method, method.

ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ВОПРОСЫ РАЗВИТИЯ МЕТОДИЧЕСКОЙ
КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ МУЗЫКИ

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Абстрактный. В статье описаны практические результаты развития методической компетентности будущих учителей музыки. Также в статье содержатся некоторые комментарии о компетентности будущего учителя музыки, умения организовать учебный процесс.

Ключевые слова. Развитие, образование, исследование, учебный процесс, развитие, среда, методическая компетентность, метод, метод.

It is desirable to develop the methodological competence of students of higher education institutions, to make them aware of innovative forms, methods and tools of education that are effective in teaching music sciences in modern conditions. For example, as a future music teacher, students need to be able to master the competence of vocal performance. Innovative methods that help students develop vocal performance skills include Seth Riggs' Speech Level

Singing (SLS), Joe Estill's Estill Voice Training (EVT), and Catherine Sadolin's It is useful to get acquainted with information about Complete Vocal Technique (CVT), to form and develop competences in using these methods. Here, brief information about these methods is provided.

1. Seth Riggs' "Speech Level Singing" (SLS) method. This method consists of a set of exercises that ensure high efficiency when performed correctly by the vocalist. By using it, the vocalist can improve voice rhythm, pitch distortion, and high pitch during the transition from note to note. prevents dissatisfaction with the voice level when going up to the curtain. The vocalist needs to know: all the secret is hidden in the way of choosing the voice when the hickel is still speaking. In this case, the voice can be used as easily and comfortably as during a conversation. Regardless, the position of the mouth and throat is the same, the timbre of the voice and the pronunciation of words (articulation) will be natural.

According to the author Seth Riggs, the main goal of the method is to have a mixed (lat. "mixtus" - "mixed" voice that sounds equally well in all registers; the voice register resonates in the chest and head). In a word, "Singing at the speech level" (Speech Level Singing (SLS) method requires singing based on the singer's physiological capabilities.

Before starting to sing, the lips are free, pushing the body a little forward, gradually working with the following voices:

Stage 1: this-this-this;

Stage 2: grandparent;

Stage 3: grandmother-grandmother-grandmother;

Step 4: Grantweight, sounds in the sound registres in the breast and thiefs of the sound; sound is as if the sound is up to top).

The general essence of the method is as follows: singing begins in a soft voice and a close position - behind the teeth, that is, the voice concentration is

heard behind the teeth; the initial way of setting the voice is to leave the body empty, to sing in a soft, soft, even a little wailing tone. The main emphasis is on singing in a "crying tone".

2. "Estill's voice training" (EOT; Estill Voice Training (EVT) method.

This method was founded by the American musician Joe Estill in the 80s of the 20th century. Joe Estill, along with many medical workers and scientists, at the Medical Center in Colton, USA, studied voice conducted systematic research. For the first time in the history of music, technical devices such as electroglottography, video stroboscopy, and electromyography were used in the research. With the help of these devices, it was possible to observe and study the state of the vocal cords during singing. served as a theoretical basis.

Even after Joe Estill's death, the research he started continued, and practical research in this direction is still being conducted today. Foreign scientists - Franco Fussi (Franco Fussi; Italy), Frank Musarra (Frank Musarra; Belgium) carried out research on the approach to Joe Estill's research, that is, on the functioning of the diaphragm during singing, and on improving work efficiency.

The method aims to consciously control the structures involved in the singing process in order to obtain the desired sound using safe means.

"Estill's voice training" (EOT; Estill Voice Training (EVT) method is a method for training the voice; it is a basic, basic system for training the voice, from which singers, actors, singers, as well as professionals who constantly work with the voice - pedagogues According to him, the understanding of the essence of the vocal work is clear, the situation that allows to achieve the desired result - from the general to the specific, in other words, the transition from the "general voice post" to the control of the structure of the individual organs that produce the vocal, is realized through strengthening the activity of the muscles (anchoring). .

Today, this method is recognized as the most effective among the methods that work with voice.

The described method puts forward the following idea: all organs in the human body participate in the formation of the voice mechanism, but each of them performs certain functions in the formation of the voice to a different degree. The Estill Voice Training (EVT) method is based on this logic and has two main components:

- 1) thirteen vocal exercises for different "figures" - organs;
- 2) six "vocal qualities" - vocal type: speech, falsetto (subtone), moaning (figon), twang (imitation; the sound of an animal, for example, the meow of a cat, imitation of the crowing of a goose), belting (in the chest created high voice), exercises designed for opera (dramatic actions and theater - a song sung based on the scene).

In the development of exercises, work is done based on the idea that "working with the abdominal muscles is somewhat unimportant, on the contrary, it is even dangerous to tighten the abdominal muscles, it is more appropriate to use other muscles involved in breathing - the body, the back of the neck, the larynx" than putting pressure on the abdominal muscles.

3. "Complete Vocal Technique" (TVT; Complete Vocal Technique (CVT) method. This method, founded by the Danish singer and researcher Catherine Sadolin in 1992, describes a unique singing technique. In the research conducted by the author, the relationship between human body physiology and vocal and related issues have been explored, and vocal enhancement using methods other than those known for music theory has been explored.

The main goal of the Complete Vocal Technique (CVT) method by Catherine Sadolin is to express the voice in a simple and understandable way and to achieve the necessary sounds in a completely natural way. Similar to Estill Voice Training (EVT).

Catherine Sadolin, studying the anatomical and physiological capabilities of singers of all types (women - soprano (high), mezzo-soprano (middle), contralto

(low); men - tenor (high), baritone (middle), bass (low) comes to the following conclusion: they all have the same common ground.

According to the results of the study, four different modes covering all human voices were distinguished: neutral (average), calm, noisy and unpleasant voice. They are discussed in detail in the work "Complete Vocal Technique" by Catherine Sadolin as an alternative textbook.

"Complete Vocal Technique" (TVT; CVT) method is a technique designed for singing in all styles, and it is based on three main principles aimed at the correct production of the voice. They are: vocal base; forced twang (imitation; the sound of an animal, for example, a cat's meow, imitating a goose's bleating); the correct position of the jaw and lips.

"Online trainers for the development of musical hearing" prepared by Russian experts. "Music Academy" methodical material in electronic format helps learners of different ages to acquire basic musical knowledge. The online trainer includes the following two types of exercises:

The exercises collected in the electronic resource are divided into two groups:

- I. Exercises that develop the ability to hear music:
 1. Determining the note by hearing.
 2. Musical dictation.
 3. Determining intervals (intervals) by hearing.

4. Determining the sequence of intervals by hearing.
5. Determining a chord (mutual unity of several sounds of different pitches) by hearing.

6. Determining the sequence of chords by hearing.

7. Determining status (lad) by hearing.

II. Music theory.

1. Identify the note.

2. Determination of the structure of intervals.

3. Determining the structure of chords.

4. Determining musical tones by basic symbols

5. Determining musical chords.

When the mouse is clicked on one of the exercises collected in the electronic resource, a new window with various tasks will open under it. For example:

Identifying a note by hearing

*Interval structure
Determination*

Defining the status structure

Determining intervals by hearing

Identifying notes

Identifying chords by hearing

1. During the substantiating experiment, attention was paid to determining their methodical competence qualities by conducting a questionnaire survey (Appendix 1) and an interview among the respondents-students.

2. The respondents' answers to the questionnaire were almost identical in content. Their responses to the survey questions were summarized as follows:

3. According to question 1: responsible performance of any work, action;

4. According to the 2nd question: performing a task, an action on time, with quality, efficiently.

5. Regarding the 3rd question: control the process of students' performance of tasks assigned to them, evaluate their knowledge;

6. According to question 4: "Musical culture", "School repertoire", "Choir and choral studies", "Traditional singing", "Vocal and modern music" are learned in the process of learning;

7. Regarding question 5: "Music culture", "School repertoire", "Choir and choral studies", "Traditional singing", "Vocal and modern music" have a great influence;

8. Regarding question 6: not to leave training sessions without reason; active participation in them; completing assignments on time; responsible approach to completing educational tasks;

9. Regarding question 7: knowledge, initiative, creativity of pedagogues; able to organize educational activities in an interesting way; a new approach to organizing lessons;

10. Regarding question 8: treating students well; taking into account their age, strength, ability when giving the task; individual work with the student; objective assessment of students' knowledge;

11. According to question 9: mastering specialized subjects that teach the basics of music education; be able to use existing knowledge in practice;

12. For question 10: textbooks, manuals, lecture texts, a set of practical tasks, a collection of laboratory works.

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